

A Syntactic Analysis of Compound Noun Phrase of Balochi within the perspective of X-bar Theory

Faraz Ahmed

MS Scholar, Faculty of Languages and Literature, Lasbela University of Agriculture,
Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal, Balochistan, Pakistan

Email: farazsarwar53@gmail.com

Zahid Ali

Associate Professor, Department of English Language and Literature, Government
College University Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

Email: zahid.ali@gcu.edu.pk

Muhammad Shoaib Khan

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Government College University
Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

Email: dr.m.shoaib@gcu.edu.pk

Muhammad Mullazai

MS Scholar, Faculty of Languages and Literature, Lasbela University of Agriculture,
Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal, Balochistan, Pakistan

Email: mohammadmullazai84@gmail.com

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Abstract

The current study aims to investigate, describe, and analyze the noun phrase of the Balochi language within the perspective of an X-bar theory. The present study seeks to describe the compound noun phrases. The work designates the structure and function of Balochi Noun phrases and analysis it in an X-bar convention. Compound noun phrases are analyzed and described under the theoretical framework of Chomsky's X-bar theory originated in 1970 then further he developed it in 1980, 81, 88. The X-bar Theory of Phrase Structures by Noam Chomsky (1980; 81; 88) was used to inform the research, particularly on the internal categories of the NP. The data for the concerned research work were collected through unstructured interviews from three native speakers of the Balochi language. For the collection of data, descriptive research design was used. The study resolute Balochi is head-last language since nearly all the elements within the Balochi Noun phrases are pre-headed. The head word of Balochi exists at the last of the phrase. Different modifiers are used within the noun phrases in Balochi. They are specifiers, complements, and adjuncts, which are used with different phrases to add extra information. Different phrases of Balochi

were used with the help of tree diagram, using an X-bar convention.

Keywords; Compound Noun phrase, X-bar theory, Complements, Tree diagram, Noun Modifiers, Pre-headed

1. Introduction

A Noun phrase is defined as a phrase which is combined of a noun or pronoun with any number of related modifiers, as well as adjectives (tall, black, smart) adjective phrases, adjectives clause, personal pronouns like (your, her, my) Adverbs like (nicely, quickly) as well as determiners (a, an, the) preposition phrases and other nouns in the possessive case. Huddleston b, R (1998) estimated that types of noun phrases are two: one is pronoun headed phrase and the other is, one noun head phrases. The head of a noun phrase is a pronoun or noun in a sentence. If the head of phrase is a noun, it might be consisted with determiners, post modifiers and pre modifiers. On the contrast, if the head is a pronoun, determiners will normally not occur in the phrase, and even if modifiers occur in a sentence, these are usually post-modifiers.

Noam Chomsky (1970) proposed the theory of X-bar at the first time. This is one of the components of Government and Binding. This theory agrees with an association among head of any phrases and other dependents inside the phrases. X-bar is a concept of syntactic class of those phrases like, VP, PP, and NP comprise in-between constituents which can be estimated excellently. An X-bar theory agrees with head group, and it shortens as well as in grammar, it elucidates the structure of phrase. This work examines Balochi compound noun phrase structure from an X- bar viewpoint.

Noun phrase is a component that is headed by an insignificant or noun. Verb phrases are headed by verbs, Prepositional phrases are headed by prepositions, and Adjective Phrases are headed by an adjective, Robin (1965). According to Alger (1995) a noun phrase is a group of words with a pronoun or noun as its head. These adds that noun can be made up by more than one word where, the collaboration within Noun phrase elements is highlighted by function of the head as well as its classification. Grounded on the statement that noun is a leading word category by which greatest meanings in the language are created, consequently, known that noun and noun phrases are essential and important in any language. In addition, the syntactic function, like subject, object, as well as the complement are mostly completed by pronoun, noun, or Noun phrases.

1.2 Origin of Balochi language

Balochi language is one of the largest western languages which is spoken mainly in Baluchistan which is separated by political borders between Iran and Afghanistan assumed by Khan and Jahani (2003). Balochi is an Iranian language, accordingly have its place to the Indo-European language, Balochi is enunciated in south eastern Iran, and south western Pakistan as well as Balochi is spoken in Arab emirate as well as in some portions of the Arabian peninsula, east Africa and India, Turkmenistan estimated by Grierson (1921 :327). Shad (2011) affirms that Balochi language concerns to the Indo-European language, which is comprised and divided in the sub branch of Iranian language family. The author further clarifies that the Balochi language has its origin from the Median languages, old Parthian and as well as Balochi language existed during the 200 B.C to 700 A.D. Bashir (1991) affirms that Balochi language belongs to the branch of Iranian Indo-European family. Elfenbein (1960)

estimated that neither Balochi was middle Persian nor Parthian (Sasanidpahalvi) was ancestor of Balochi language, relatively it was a lost language which shared a number of characteristic landscapes with either some or both and had expounded individuality of its own. Baloch (2014) estimated that Balochi is the oldest form of the modern Persian languages.

According to Mackenzie (1961) the speakers of Iranian languages Persian, Kurdish and Balochi have been in near contact ethnically and geographically. It can be observed by the works of Windfuhr (1975). He took out that numerous connections between Kurdish Persian and Balochi on morphological and cultural level. Korn (2003) kept the Balochi language among the western Iranian languages family. In the sense of being a third member he classified Iranian languages between north and southwestern of earliest language. Balochi language shares the same structures to both Parthian and middle Persian which is a historical region located in northeastern Iran.

Shad (2011) has classified and categorized Balochi language into three main dialects which are Makrani dialect, Rakhshani dialect and Kohe Sulamani dialect. Makrani dialect is spoken in district kech, Karachi to coastal areas of Balochistan including Gwadar, Pasani, Ormara, Lasbela, also coastal areas of Iran like Chabahar and Arabistan. Rakhshani dialect is spoken in North and North-east of Balochistan (Kharan, Kalat, Awaran, Chaghi, Noshki, Kharan, Panjgur and Quetta Division). The people of Kohe Sulieman, Bughti and Mari, Bolan, Dera Ghazi Khan, Naseer Abad, Sarawan, Dera Ismail Khan and Sibi speak Kohe Sulemani dialect (Ahmed, M., & Veesar, Z. A., 2022; Hanan, et al., 2021).

1.3 Research concern

The current study aims to investigate, describe, and analyze the noun phrase of the Balochi language within the perspective of an X-bar theory. The present study seeks to describe the compound phrases. The work designates the structure and function of Balochi Noun phrases and analysis it in an X-bar convention.

The current research work describes, the compound Noun phrase in the Balochi language. These compound phrases are used within the framework of X-bar theory Chomsky (1970). The consignment of compound noun phrases in Balochi may help the researcher to understand this phenomenon in concerned of Balochi language. Numerous fresh grammarians and other linguists gave their involvement in field of syntax, Morphology and Semantics. There is no adequate study on Balochi compound noun phrases within the perspective of X-bar theory. In this field, it is an additional work in Balochi grammar especially in the field of syntax. The current study deals with the compound noun phrases within the perspective of X-bar theory. The present study emphasizes to discover the use of Balochi compound noun phrases using X-bar convention. This study may also be helpful for the society and for the Balochi language.

1.4 Objective of the study

The main purpose of the current research is to analyze Balochi noun phrase within the perspective of X-bar theory. It tries to understand the compound noun phrases with the help of tree diagram using x-bar convention. It also tries to scrutinize that how Balochi compound noun phrases play their role in field of syntax.

2. Noun Phrase

A phrase is introduced as a grammatical component that is prepared by a head which is surrounded by any one element or more than one element. A phrase is a combination of words which has no subject, such definitions point out that a phrase is greater than a head however it is controlled by a head. From such points of interpretation, it is obviously shown that a phrase is completed by the clusters of words including function words and lexical words however, the lexical word is what heads the phrase as well as from where the name of specific phrase is created.

According to Robin (1965), a head is a main or the fundamental word in any kind of phrase. A main or fundamental word, which can stand separately as a complete phrase and that can be modified by other components which are observed as complements or specifics. Therefore, a head is a main component which is also, a core and obligatory word though other dependents are mentioned to as, Noun phrase modifiers. Noun phrase is a component that is headed by an insignificant or noun. Verb phrases are headed by verbs, Prepositional phrases are headed by prepositions, and Adjective Phrases are headed by an adjective, Robin (1965). According to Alger (1995) a noun phrase is a group of words with a pronoun or noun as its head. These adds that noun can be made up by more than one word where, the collaboration within Noun phrase elements is highlighted by function of the head as well as its classification. Grounded on the statement that noun is a leading word category by which greatest meanings in the language are created, consequently, known that noun and noun phrases are essential and important in any language. In addition, the syntactic function, like subject, object, as well as the complement are mostly completed by pronoun, noun, or Noun phrases.

2.2 Conditions Used in Classifying the NP Elements

According to Carnie (2006) deliberates the criteria used to allocate the words to their appropriate word classes, namely, semantic, or tradition criteria. Concerning the semantic conditions, any word is allocated to its group by seeing its meaning. For instance, noun is well-defined as a name of person, thing, or place. Such weakness of this principles is that it would be tough to allocate word with numerous meanings to its proper word group. In contrast, the distributional principles allocate words to its group based on two distributional, known as the morphological distributional as well as the syntactic distributional.

Morphological distribution concerns with some of the affixes which are involved to words. Such affixes make words from other words hereafter, they are occasionally mentioned to as, derivational morphemes. For example, -er, -lly, -ly, -est. The weakness of this condition is that more or less morphemes, such as (-ly) is used in more than one group and, hereafter, they merely be dependent on the morphological distribution that is not suited. To rely on syntactic distribution, as words are categorized to their groups created on how words select other words or other members to seem with, also before or after in the creation. Now, the concern is Noun phrase construction. For instance, in English Noun phrase, which is likely, to say that adjectives are usually positioned before the head as revealed in the illustration below. A beautiful car. NP= (DET) + (ADJ) + (N) The description of this condition is that they are exact to English whereas numerous studies expose that all languages have their own distributional Carnie (2005). The present study, consequently, has used all the three conditions in the

identification of the components surround the Balochi NP also

2.3 Morphology of Balochi noun

According to Jahani (2019) a noun is a word which discusses a person, an animate means (living animal) or inanimate (nonliving things) object, or discusses an abstract concept. It can act as the subject of a verb, (for instance, the girl talks), direct object of a verb (for instance she saw the cake), indirect object of a verb, (for instance, he gave the girl a watch). A genitive attribute representing possession or an ownership-like relation to other word (for instance, I met the man's daughter), the object of an ad position which is known is postposition or preposition (for example, she has some news of the teacher), or an adverbial (we saw the man this evening). Such as English, but dissimilar from other languages.

Obviously, Balochi has no gender distinctions in the noun systems. A noun can be declined, which gives the meaning that its form is changed as soon as it is used in several syntactic roles in sentences. For instance, as a subject, as a direct object as well as a genitive attribute. In Balochi case forms are direct also called nominative case, oblique case, object case, genitive case, and vocative case.

2.4 Theory of X-Bar phrase structure

According to Radford (1988) claims that the traditional part of speech has undertaken different alteration since their inception between Roman Grammarians. In the words of Comish (1986), Harris (1951), Chomsky (1976) claim that there were issues with phrasal and lexical categories. The problem is that they required another kind of category among phrasal and lexical categories. So new level is known as X-Bar category. In X-Bar Chomsky (1965) expounded that phrases are endocentric. This means that all phrases have different features in its making. Like X is the head of that phrase. In the original X-Bar theory, there are different phrases like verb phrase, adjective phrase, prepositional phrase, and noun phrase etc. In noun phrases there are two different entities, one is NP and other is N-bar.

X-Bar theory makes the claim that every phrase has a head in the mental grammar of single human language, which has the similar core organization. Only difference occurs on their head words because there are head initial and head last languages. According to universal grammar, English is head initial while other all local languages are head last languages. According to X-bar theory every phrase has a head which is the terminal node of that particular phrase. It is the node that has no daughters. The head word always determines the category of that phrase. Like if the head is a verb (V) it becomes a verb phrase, if the head is a noun so the phrase becomes a noun phrase (NP). In tree diagrams the bottom level of structure is called the head level, while the top level is called phrase level and middle level is called bar level.

3 Research Methodology

Descriptive method has been applied in the present work. This work has employed qualitative method of research (Creswell, 2013; Neuman, 2005; Kumar, 2011; 2014). The Balochi language spoken form or verbal form is designated in order to understand the terms, nature and normally the function of the nouns. The main purpose of this research is to study and describe how noun phrases are used within the perspective of X-bar theory.

The data are collected through interviews from specific native Balochi speakers. Unstructured interviews are the most popular primary data collection method with exploratory studies and this type of interview is selected during the study. The participants are asked personal questions, their names and about their family first. They have also been asked about their professional lives, and the participants had enough confidence to communicate more freely, frankly, fluently, confidently in a natural way.

Through unstructured interviews to see and observe the role of generative grammar, morphology and syntax in oral form of Balochi. Oral form of Balochi language will be taken for the descriptive study of Balochi compound noun phrases within the perspective of X-bar theory proposed by Chomsky (1970) of formal syntax on the spoken Balochi focusing on the compound noun phrases.

3.1 Theoretical/Conceptual framework

The present study employed the X-bar theory of phrase structure and syntactic function. According to Carnie (2006), X-bar theory is the generative theory of grammar, in which internal structure of syntactic constituents concerns with this theory, which place constraints for the rules of phrase structure. This theory was first developed by Noam Chomsky (1970), later on it was developed by Jekendoff (1977) and after that it was developed by Radford (1988). Formula of X-bar theory:

X-bar theory is obviously based on the assumption that prominent phrases have a head, which determines the name of that phrase. That phrase is also known as a terminal node Carnie (2006). Such as VP, NP, PP, ADJP, and ADVP, are the maximal projection in the phrase. As the head of the phrase X-bar theory puts much emphasis on lexical category rather than functional categories. Obligatory part in any phrase is considered its head. X-bar theory suggests that every phrase must be presented into three level, maximal projection (XP), which is arbitrary, can be used as VP, NP, ADJP, ADVP. Intermediate level is (X'), and (X) which can be a complement or specifier.

3.2 Data Analysis

The data were investigated with the support of the theoretical framework. This X-bar theory was first developed by Noam Chomsky (1970). The Balochi compound noun phrases were defined, and described to understand their task, place, and significance in phrase structure. The data were also described in order to understand how Balochi nouns are used within the framework of X-bar theory. Additionally, the data in this research were also analyzed permitted to see how the settings of the nouns pay with respect to the meaning of the noun in a phrase.

3.3 Compound Nouns

Compound nouns are words for things, people, places, animals, or ideas. Many compound nouns are made with nouns that have been modified by nouns or adjectives. In most of compound nouns, the very first words describe or modify the second word. Sometimes

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compound nouns are words like, bedroom, airport, and toothpaste in English. As well as some compound nouns are connected with hyphen: for example, son-in law. According to Jahani (2019), in attendance number of productive word-formation prefixes as well as suffixes are in the Balochi language.

Example 1: shows Balochi Compound noun phrase, kasanin kawrjoh/ Small River, used within the framework of an X-bar theory, using tree diagram

S#	Coding	Phrase Description	Phrase
1	M	(Roman) (Balochi) (Translation) (Transliteration)	Kasanin kawrjoh کسانين کورجو Small River Kasanin=کسانين=small, kawrjoh=کورجو=river
NP			
		Kahsanin (ADJ) NP= ADJ + N	(N) kawrjoh

The above given example 1 is following an adjective and a compound noun. In this Balochi compound noun phrase 'kasanin=کسانين=small' is an adjective, 'kawrjoh=کورجو=river' is a compound noun. The cited phrase is used within the framework of X-bar theory and explained with the help of tree diagram. The above cited phrase is noun phrase, where the head word is being modified by an adjective. The head word of this phrase is 'kawrjoh=کورجو=river', which is the head of this phrase. According to X-bar theory every phrase has a head, which is the obligatory element of that particular phrase. A phrase is always known by its head. Every natural language of the world has their own head, some of them are in right and some of them are in left. According to universal Grammar which posits that all world languages have common universal principles and language specific rules, which differ from language-to-language Chomsky (1981; 86; 88). Universal grammar expounded that all local languages are head last languages, such as Balochi is a head last language, where head comes at the last of phrase.

Noun is a word that refers to a person, living and non-living things. Adjectives are words which qualifies noun, simultaneously gives additional information about adverb and noun Jahani, (2019). Most compound nouns are made with nouns that have been modified by adjectives or other nouns. In this phrase kashanin/small is an adjective which qualifies on the noun that is kawrjoh/river, which is also working as the head of this phrase. The head word 'kawrjoh/river' is a combination of two words, 'kwar=کور' which means a big river, while 'joh=جو' means a small river. The main water runs through kawr=کور, which is quite deep and large, while the water of joh=جو, flows in a small quantity. So, this word is a combination of two different words, but in this phrase, it is giving a single meaning and working as the head word of the cited phrase.

According to uniformity principle and universal grammar, some of the languages are headfirst languages and some are head last languages. English is head initial language while Urdu and other such local languages are head last languages like Pashto and Balochi.

Eventually Balochi is a head last language in which the head word exists at the last. The difference between Balochi and English phrase is the position of head word in word order. Meanwhile Balochi is head last language. The cited phrase was uttered by the interviewee during unstructured interview without any subject or helping verb etc. it's clear in the aforementioned phrase that the head word of this phrase is 'kawrjoh/river/کورجو'. The head word is modified by an adjective that is 'khsanin/small/کسانين', that added extra information to the cited phrase.

Example 2: is a Compound noun phrase in Balochi, Mani wanagjah/ my school, is used within the framework of an X-bar theory and explained with the help of tree diagram.

S#	Coding	Phrase Description	Phrase
2	M	(Roman) (Balochi) (Translation) (Transliteration)	Mani wanagjah مَنِي وَاَنگ جَاه My school Mani=my=مَنِي , wanagjah= وَاَنگ جَاه =school

NP= DET+N

The above-mentioned phrase is a compound noun phrase. Apparently, the entire noun phrase is consisting of a determiner and a noun. Evidently a compound noun is a single word formed by the morphological combination of two different words. Noun in the above phrase that is wanagjah is a combination of two words, wanag/وَاَنگ, which means to study, and jah/جَاه, means place. The cited word together give or convey a single meaning in Balochi. In the cited phrase Mani wanagjah, / مَنِي وَاَنگ جَاه /, my school is a compound noun phrase in Balochi, which was uttered by the interviewee during unstructured interview. The above-mentioned phrase is following a determiner, which is a possessive pronoun in Balochi that is 'Mani=مَنِي =my', it shows belonging and add extra information to the phrase. Apparently, the entire noun phrase structure is consisting of a single noun. Noun is the prominent element that make a head in an NP. Both common and proper noun stands as the head within a noun phrase.

The findings also discovered that the NP in Balochi is categorized into three types, this includes simple noun phrase which are made by nouns, pronouns, and modifiers, like demonstratives and distributors. On the other hand, compound and complex noun phrases are always followed by modifiers, relative clauses etc.

Noun works as the subject or object of the clause which consists of articles, adjectives, and adverbs. Compound noun is composed of two or more individual nouns combined together. This phrase is consisted of a possessive pronoun, 'Mani/مَنِي/my' which is showing possession to the phrase. It clears the phrase that 'wanagjah/school' belongs to this person. Possessive pronouns are words which show ownership and used instead of noun. It refers to a specific person/people or thing etc. The cited Balochi compound noun phrase is used within the framework of X-bar theory. X-bar theory makes the simple proposal that every phrase in every language of the world has organized the same law and rules but only difference exists between their head words. The head word of this phrase is 'wanagjah= وَاَنگ جَاه =school'.

Example 3: presents a compound Noun phrase in Balochi, ‘skooli kitabjah’, school’s book is used within the framework of X-bar theory, using tree diagram.

S#	Coding	Phrase Description	Phrase
3	N	(Roman) (Persian) (Translation) (Transliteration)	Skooli kitabjah اسکولی کتاب جاہ School’s book place Skooli=اسکولی=school’s, kitab= کتاب جاہ=place of books
NP			
NP= N+N			

The above-mentioned phrase is a compound noun phrase in Balochi. Apparently, the entire noun phrase structure is consisting of double noun. The interviewee uttered this phrase during unstructured interview. Where he uttered two nouns together and made a complete noun phrase in Balochi. The cited phrase is skooli/school/اسکولی, kitabjah/book/کتاب جاہ. School’s book place is used within the framework of an X-bar theory using tree diagram. Which gives priority to the head word, which is the obligatory element in that particular phrase. Universal grammar posits that all world languages have common universal principle and language specific rules or parameters. Languages differ from each other only in parametric setting and their rule of head words, Chomsky (1957). However, within this principle each language has its own rules such as head-first language and head last language Chomsky (1957).

In the aforementioned phrase, two nouns are uttered during unstructured interview, at the first of the phrase a noun is showing possession, skooli=اسکولی=school’s, in here possessive is used to show relationship between something and referred by describing ownership Jahani (2019). Secondly the interviewee uttered a compound noun in Balochi, kitabjah/book/کتاب جاہ which is a combination of two words, kitab means book and jah means place. Together this word conveys a single meaning which means a place where books are kept.

Seemingly the above captioned phrase is having two nouns, in which the very first noun which is uttered by the speaker that shows possession, while other is a common noun which is working as the head of the phrase. The mentioned phrase is not conveying a complete meaning and sense, but the Balochi speakers can utter such phrases, and the listeners have the linguistic competence to recover, infer and identify what the speaker wants to say. The noun phrase ‘skooli=اسکولی=school’s, kitaab=کتاب جاہ=book place’ in the mentioned phrase with the help of tree diagram does not carry any subject, but with the help of associated properties which conveys a half meaning but make a complete Balochi compound noun phrase. In the cited phrase the last noun kitaab=کتاب جاہ=’ which is a common noun in Balochi working as the head word of this phrase because a phrase is always known by its head word.

Example 4: English compound noun phrase, ‘Hamey Nadrajah’ our hospital, is used within the framework of an X-bar theory.

S#	Coding	Phrase Description	Phrase
4	N	(Roman) (Persian)	Hamey nadrajah همیے نادره جاہ

In the above-mentioned example of compound noun phrase of Balochi hamey Nadra jah/our hospital. In this phrase, 'Nadrajah/hospital' is a morphological combination of two words, the base word is 'Nadra نادره' means ill, and 'jah/جَاه' means place. In the beginning of the phrase a determiner is used to modify the noun. The cited determiner is a possessive pronoun in Balochi that is, 'hamey/همے/our' is used to show belonging and added extra information to the phrase. The cited possessive pronoun is used with a simple noun, which refers to a common place.

The cited phrase is used within the framework of X-bar theory. The idea behind X-bar theory is the recognition of the fact that most phrasal categories have heads upon which elements of the constituent in questions are dependent, Chomsky (1965). As the phrase can be seen clearly on a tree diagram within the framework of an X-bar theory. In the above-mentioned phrase, a determiner is used to modify the noun, in the cited phrase determiner is a possessive pronoun, which is used to show relationship between a person and referred to describe ownership.

Example 5: presents a compound noun phrase in Balochi, 'mani wabjah' is used within the framework of an X-bar theory, using tree diagram.

The above-mentioned phrase is a compound noun phrase in Balochi, which is used within the framework of an X-bar theory Chomsky (1980; 81; 88). The above cited phrase is a compound noun phrase which is followed by a determiner in Balochi. From rules of NP that is observed that (N) noun is the obligatory element in any noun phrase. In the aforementioned phrase 'wabjah/bedroom/ وَا ب جَاه' is the head word where two nouns are combined together, to convey a single meaning. One is 'wab' which means sleep and the other is 'jah', which means place Jahani (2019). The interviewee's main focus in the phrase is the compound noun, which also plays the role of the head word.

According to Carnie (2006) NP other noun head materials that are optional work as either complement, adjunct, or specifiers. As in the mentioned phrase a determiner is used to introduce the noun. There are four types of determiners, one of them is a possessive pronoun, which is uttered by the interviewee that is 'mani/مَنی/my' is a possessive pronoun in Balochi which shows possession as well as add extra information to the phrase and clears the

meaning and convey a better sense in understanding. The mentioned phrase is not conveying a complete meaning and sense, but the Balochi speakers can utter such phrases and the listeners have the linguistic competence and command to infer and identify what the speaker wants to say. Noun phrases are always modified by other modifiers Such as specifiers like article, adjunct etc. They are important in building the relationship between the dependent and the head noun.

Head principle of universal grammar UG declares that heads occur in structure of world natural languages. As some languages are known as head last language and some are head initial. According to uniformity principle and universal grammar, English is head initial language where head exists at the starting of a sentence or phrase, while other languages like Urdu and other local languages where head exists at the last.

Example 6: shows compound noun phrase in Baloch, Tahi Nakozagh, your cousin, is used within the framework of X-bar theory using tree diagram.

S#	Coding	Phrase Description	Phrase
6	M	(Roman)	Tahi Nakozagh
		(Persian)	تہی ناکوزہگ
		(Translation)	Your cousin
		(Transliteration)	Tahi=تہی=your, nakozagh=ناکوزہگ=cousin.
		NP	
		Tahi (DET)	
			NP=DET+N

Example 6 shows the noun structure of the Balochi language, where the interviewee utilizes ‘Tahi=تہی=your’ at the subject place. ‘Tahi=تہی= your’ is a determiner. Determiner is a word that occurs with a noun or noun phrase that generally serves to express the reference of that noun phrase or noun in the context. There are four types of determiners, they are demonstrative, possessive, quantifiers, and articles Jahani (2019). The cited determiner is a possessive pronoun which shows belonging that is positioned immediately before the compound noun. That is ‘nakozagh/ناکوزہگ/cousin’. The data in aforementioned phrase reveal something which is very important about Balochi possessive that agrees and modify the head word that is ‘nakozagh/ناکوزہگ/cousin’, semantically it agrees with the noun which is being expounded. The mentioned phrase is not conveying a complete meaning and sense, but the Balochi speakers can utter such phrases and the listeners have the linguistic competence to recover, infer and identify what the speaker wants to say.

In the cited noun phrase, it is corresponding a noun which is a combination of two words, ‘Nako= ناکو’, which means uncle and ‘zagh’ زہگ that means child. Here also it’s not clear that the interviewee is talking about a male or female because there is no gender marker in Balochi.

The aforementioned phrase is used within the framework of an X-bar theory, using tree diagram. According to X-bar theory a phrase must be consisted of a head which plays a consequence role, and a phrase is always known by its head. According to Head principle of UG that head occurs in the structure of all languages of the world. Head means the head of any phrase, like adjective phrase, prepositional phrase, adverb phrase etc. some languages are headfirst languages, and some are head last languages. In talking about head parameter, we are concerned with the place of head in different languages.

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Example 7: is a compound noun in Balochi, Aah karghis, that office is used within the framework of an X-bar theory, using tree diagram.

S#	Coding	Phrase Description	Phrase
7	N	(Roman) (Persian) (Translation) (Transliteration)	Aah karghis ها کارگس That office Ah=ها=that, karghis=کارگس=office.
NP			
		NP=DET+N	

The above instance 7 as shown that declares the structure of Balochi compound phrase within the framework of an X-bar theory using the tree diagram. The above phrase shows that it is following a determiner, which is modifying the head word and adding extra information to the cited phrase. The cited determiner is a demonstrative, such demonstratives are found to form the elements which perform the role of determiner. The main function of demonstrative as observed in such NP is to locate the referent in relation to a speaker an addressee or some other person. Demonstratives are used to show concordial agreement with the head noun. In the context of noun phrase, the cited phrase is following a demonstrative to show locate.

The cited phrase of Balochi compound noun phrase was uttered by the interviewee during unstructured interview. The cited phrase Aah=that=ها, and 'karghis=کارگس=office' is a compound noun phrase, where a compound noun was uttered by the interviewee. In the above phrase two nouns are used together to convey a single meaning. One is 'kar', which means work and other is 'ghis' that means room. In this phrase 'karghis/office', is used as a single word to convey a single meaning. Compound noun can be written either as a single word, as words with hyphen in English, because there is no clear rule for this. From the rule of NP, it is clear that every phrase has a head. Head principle of UG says that 'heads' occur in the structure of world languages. In the aforementioned phrase of Balochi 'Karghis=کارگس=office' is the head word of this phrase because the speaker's main focus is compound noun which plays the role of head word in the cited phrase. In the cited phrase two words are used to form a single word, as the word 'karghis=کارگس=office' is used in the cited phrase. 'Kar' means work and 'ghis' means house, both words are combined together to convey a single meaning. Compounding derives a new word by joining two different morphemes that would be free morphemes.

In the cited phrase a common noun is uttered by the interviewee during unstructured interview. According to Jahani (2019) Common nouns are all the other nouns that in themselves do not mention to a specific thing, individual, animal, concept, such as 'math' 'mother', 'sangāt /friend' etc. On the other hand, Proper nouns are names of specific things, individuals, animals, or concepts, such as, 'Balach' (name of a man), 'Makkoranay Zer' (The Sea of Makran). Mostly they are capitalized in the Balochi-Latin script. In the aforementioned phrase 'karghis' is a common noun and working as the head word of the cited phrase.

Example 8: is a compound noun phrase in Balochi 'Mani Aramjah' my grave, is used within the framework of X-bar theory and explained with the help of tree diagram.

S#	Coding	Phrase Description	Phrase
9	M	(Roman) (Persian) (Translation) (Transliteration)	Mani Aramjah منی آرام جاه My grave Mani= منی=my, Aramjah= آرام=grave
		NP Mani (DET)	<pre> graph TD NP[NP] --- Mani["Mani (DET)"] NP --- Aramjah["Aramjah (N)"] </pre>
		NP=DET+N	

In the light of the example 8 shows that it is a phrase of the Balochi language, the nature of the compound phrase is used with a determiner. The cited phrase is being used within the framework of an X-bar theory. The cited NP is used with the help of tree diagram in which the compound noun is being followed by a determiner, which may indicate whether the noun is showing possession, or shows belonging. The cited determiner is a possessive pronoun that is Mani/my/منی, is showing possession or belonging. In the light of this phrase the compound noun which is used after the possessive pronoun that is the head word too. According to X-bar theory every phrase must have a head which performs the obligatory element of that phrase.

In the cited phrase the noun which is Aramjah/grave=آرام جاه is the head word, where interviewee's main focus is based. Accordingly compound noun can be written either with hyphen, in single word or with two words which are attached together. The cited compound noun which is working as the head word of this phrase is a common noun in Balochi. Compounding derives new words by constructing two different morphemes that would be free morphemes. Morphemes can be usually either single words or parts of other words. If two morphemes are joined together, they make a single word and gives a complete meaning. In the cited phrase Aramjah/ آرام جاه is a compound noun, where two words are used together that conveys a single meaning. 'Aram'/ آرام which means rest, and 'jah'=جاه that means place. The cited compound noun conveys a single meaning and work as the head word of this phrase.

Huddleston (1988) states that a noun phrase is a major constituent which is made by a noun as its head. Noun is a head of a phrase that can stand alone or can be accompanied by one or more element as its dependent. According to Dryden (2007), there are three types of NP namely simple noun, compound noun, and complex noun. Simple nouns consist of a noun, or some modifiers are used to add extra information to that noun. Compound and complex nouns are made by noun and other modifiers such as possessive, relative clause, etc. in any language personal pronouns are very important elements.

4. Discussion and findings

The current study draws results and findings for compound noun phrases of the Balochi language, which has explained with the help of tree diagram. The explained phrases are used according to Chomsky's theory. X-bar theory is a theory of phrase structure which establishes a possible phrase mostly in natural languages of the world. In current study, complex noun phrases of Balochi have been used with the help of tree diagram with different modifiers, like adjunct, adjective, cardinal numerals etc. (Shazia, et al., 2022; Khan, et al., 2022)

Different Balochi phrases were used within the framework of X-bar theory using tree

diagram. The Balochi complement branch at X'. To expound this, complements are sister to the head noun and daughters to N'. These complements are modifiers that add extra information to the particular phrase. Specifiers in Balochi can happen on the right because Balochi is head last language where head word of the phrase exists at the last of the phrase. According to UG principle, English is head initial language while local languages like Sindhi, Urdu, Persian, Balochi and other local languages are head last languages (Bagudu, et. al., 2015; Zahid, A., 2016; Ali, Z., & Azam, M., 2021; Ali, Z., Roonjho, Z., & Brohi, 2021; Veasar, et al., 2015a and b; Veasar, Z. A., Pathan, M. S. K. (2023), Pathan, M. S. K. (2022), Pathan, M. S. K. (2022) & Mustafa, 2021). It is observed that the Balochi Noun phrases can be investigated using an X-bar theory. The rules permit cross-linguistic differences whereby the components can happen on the right of the noun phrases. The analysis declares that in Balochi different phrases can be uttered like English, Persian, Italian, Brahvi, and Urdu. Native speakers and hearers of Balochi have the potentiality and credibility to infer, identify and regain such phrases and they are capable to use such phrase in their daily spoken. Different phrases are inferable, interpretable, and recoverable to both the native Balochi speakers and listeners who have innate linguistic or communicative competence to utilize and understand compound noun phrases of Balochi.

5 Conclusion

In the pursuit to comprehend linguistic theory, X-bar and noun phrases, an attempt is made to analyze Balochi compound Noun phrases syntactically with the help of tree diagram. The objective of the study was accomplished, in accumulation, the investigation conventions were authenticated that there are numerous features that found noun phrase structures in Balochi, Balochi noun phrases can be accounted for using an X-bar and that Balochi noun phrases have syntactic function within an X-bar theory

6 Recommendations

The study discussed the compound noun phrase of Balochi and its syntactic functions within X-bar. A similar work can be conducted to prevent other language extinction. Furthermore the present study only concerns on compound noun phrases of the Balochi language. In addition, Sentences of Balochi language and other phrases also need to be described within the perspective of X-bar theory using tree diagram. This study only discussed the compound noun phrases of Balochi and its syntactic functions within X-bar. Lastly, the findings from this work can also be useful to the teachers, learners, linguists, and Balochi people.

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